

Case Studies

TOOLSHEET

Purpose

There is no need to reinvent the wheel when applying a multi-actor approach. The underlying principles have been tested and practiced across many contexts for years. Often, what is most useful is not a new framework, but a concrete example (or simply a spark of inspiration) that shows how others have tackled similar challenges.

Benefits

Learning from the experiences of previous projects can accelerate your own work. Tools and methodologies are useful in theory, but examples of real-world application reveal how they function in practice. Such case studies open a window into the successes and challenges faced by others. At the very least, they can provide inspiration; at best, they offer tested insights directly transferable to your own context.

Practical recommendations

Two key sources provide accessible entry points to multi-actor case studies. The [LIAISON's Innovative Case Studies](#) collection on Zenodo offers in-depth analyses dedicated to the multi-actor approach. In addition, the [EU CAP Network](#) project database allows you to search specifically for projects meeting multi-actor criteria, enabling you to explore diverse practices and approaches firsthand.

Applicability box

Main MA Skills supported

Transparent communication about agenda's, expectations and results

Be comfortable with co-ownership and responsibility of tasks, results, and outcomes

Relevant Target groups

Useful link(s)

[LIAISON's Innovative Case Studies](#)

[EU CAP Network](#)

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